

SOP: 3D Reference Object Approval

Process for approving a 3D reference object model for integration into the EUI and RUI tools

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NIH Award No: OT2OD026671

Updated: February 1, 2022

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Introduction

The procedures outlined in this document describe how 3D reference objects are designed and revised by the Medical Illustrator, and how subject matter experts (SMEs) are selected, as well as how these experts review and approve these 3D reference objects. Models appear under the [3D Reference Object Library](#) on the [CCF Portal](#) and are used in the [Registration User Interface](#) (RUI) and [Exploration User Interface](#) (EUI). The 3D reference objects are a critical part of the evolving Human Reference Atlas. See (Börner et al. 2021) for background information.

This document is intended for medical illustrators and subject matter experts (SMEs) involved in the 3D reference object approval process, many of whom are organ experts from funded components of HuBMAP or other projects.

Roles and Responsibilities

Different types of expertise are required to author and approve 3D reference objects and major roles are listed below. [Table 1](#) identifies the people occupying these roles.

A **Subject Matter Expert (SME)** is a person with extensive knowledge about a given topic. In the procedures addressed here, the SME ensures that 3D models are designed in an anatomically correct manner. The procedures followed by the SME are designed to ensure that the 3D models are designed using a process that requires minimal corrections and design iterations.

The **Senior Research Analyst-Biologist** is the 3D Modeler's main contact in the MC-IU team. They provide the information and resources the Medical Illustrator needs and facilitate communication between the Medical Illustrator and the SME(s) throughout the process of building an organ. S/he meets with the Medical Illustrator weekly to determine modeling progress and to remove blocks. S/he compiles and shares a gross-anatomical list of terms and ensures this list is part of the relevant Anatomical Structures, Cell Types plus Biomarkers (ASCT+B) table (Börner et al. 2021; HuBMAP Consortium 2021).

The **Medical Illustrator** designs 3D models based on the approved gross-anatomical list of terms obtained from SME(s). S/he negotiates and implements changes suggested by SME(s), obtains final approval from the SME(s) and uploads the models for use in HuBMAP services and user interfaces.

The **Systems Architect** uses the 3D objects in the Registration User Interface (RUI) and Exploration User Interface (EUI). The Systems Architect provides technical expertise in the areas of 3D model storage options and the integration of the 3D models into the HuBMAP ecosystem (e.g., how structures should be labeled to work well with existing ontology schemas).

The **Principal Investigator (PI)** holds final responsibility for delivering anatomically correct 3D models for use in the HuBMAP Human Reference Atlas. The PI approves budgets associated with the 3D reference object modeling process, hires relevant experts, sets high-level goals and associated deadlines, attends meetings, and reviews notes and recordings from relevant meetings between the Senior Research Analyst-Biologist and Medical Illustrator, as needed.

Table 1. Roles, names, and email addresses of key personnel.

Role	Name	Email
Subject Matter Expert (SME)	Depends on organ	
Medical Illustrator	Heidi Schlehlein	hschlehlein@gmail.com
Senior Research Analyst-Biologist	Ellen Quardokus	ellenmq@iu.edu
Systems Architect	Bruce W. Herr II	bherr@iu.edu
Principal Investigator (PI)	Katy Börner	katy@iu.edu

Workflow

Step 1: Identifying SME(s) for Design and Review of Model

- When a new organ is selected for inclusion in the HuBMAP Human Reference Atlas (HRA), the PI or Senior Research Analyst-Biologist identifies 1-3 SMEs.
 - a. Selection is made from experts researching the organ within HuBMAP, when possible
 - b. Experts outside HuBMAP may be invited
 - c. If the same SME is also creating an ASCT+B table for the organ, emphasize this task is only for the gross anatomy and a separate simple list is needed.

Step 2: On-Boarding SMEs

- The Senior Research Analyst-Biologist customizes the [email template](#) that contains relevant on-boarding resources for SMEs.
- The Senior Research Analyst-Biologist sends an initial email to the SME(s), pointing them to this SOP.
- The Senior Research Analyst-Biologist orients each SME to the task by providing the following information:
 - a. an overview of the roles outlined in this SOP, who occupies these roles, and why they are needed.
 - b. the scope (see above) of MC-IU's user interfaces (UIs) for HuBMAP, e.g., the RUI and EUI.
 - c. how the 3D reference organ models are used in these UIs.
 - d. that SME input is essential for the successful implementation and inclusion of 3D models in the MC-IU UIs.
 - e. how the 3D model review process works. See [below](#).
- The Senior Research Analyst-Biologist requests that the SME provide their ORCID(s) via this [registration form](#) for the ASCT+B Working Group.
- At this time, the Senior Research Analyst-Biologist also shares videos and other demo materials about the RUI, EUI, and organ review process (outlined in the SME Review section below) including:
 - a. A [RUI demo](#), to be updated with every major RUI release.
 - b. An [EUI demo](#), to be updated with every major RUI release (same link as RUI but later in the video).
 - c. A [demo](#) of how to use Babylon.js Sandbox. For the best experience, use either Firefox or Chrome as a browser.
 - d. Written instructions for how to use Babylon.js Sandbox can be found [here](#).
 - e. A version history of the CCF user interfaces can be found at <https://github.com/hubmapconsortium/ccf-ui/blob/main/CHANGELOG.md>.

Step 3: Gathering Requirements

- The Senior Research Analyst-Biologist establishes initial contact between the SME(s) and the Medical Illustrator via email.
- The Senior Research Analyst-Biologist emphasizes the scope of the 3D reference model, noting that the collection of a gross anatomy parts listing for this effort is separate from the ASCT+B table effort and that time requirements will be much shorter. A gross-anatomical list of terms obtained and approved from SME(s) for their organ model [here](#) will be incorporated into the relevant ASCT+B table.
- It is crucial to state that the gross anatomy can be separated from the ASCT+B table, which is focused on cell types and biomarkers, but that the gross anatomy should also be put into the ASCT+B table.
- If the SMEs involved in the 3D model building are different from those authoring the ASCT+B table, then the gross anatomy parts listing must be communicated to the ASCT+B Table Lead authors for inclusion.

Scope of the 3D Reference Model

3D reference model gross anatomical structures list should include:

- The minimal anatomical structures and landmarks needed to accurately place a block in the tissue registration tool we have called the Registration User Interface (RUI).
- The list should only include macroscopic structures.
- Structures should be named according to a standard convention often seen in anatomy texts or clinical applications to facilitate identification in anatomy ontologies such as Uber anatomy (Uberon) or Foundational Model of Anatomy (FMA) (Mungall et al. 2012; Golbreich, Grosjean, and Darmoni 2013; Rosse and Mejino 2003)).
- Note that ONLY what is on the list will be built, so all structures needed for orientation or evaluation purposes must be on the parts list.
- Note that we will not add vasculature or nerves unless specifically asked for at this stage, so please indicate if they are necessary for any reason.
- This list is a “wish list”. We will try our best to include everything that is possible; however, too many overlapping surfaces and landmarks can become confusing to evaluate and use in the EUI/RUI, so we encourage being reasonably conservative.
- The Medical Illustrator may request a call to answer organ-specific questions, establish a specific work mode, or review existing and prior work that could help build the 3D model. All calls are recorded and meetings notes are taken. The recordings and meeting notes are available from the Senior Research Analyst-Biologist upon request. This initial meeting (unless deemed unnecessary by the Medical Illustrator) covers the following topics:
 - a. The Senior Research Analyst-Biologist provides a brief overview of how the organs will be used.
 - b. The SME confirms that they have understood this SOP, and asks any remaining questions.

- c. The Senior Research Analyst-Biologist prepares and shares with the SME a list of gross-anatomical terms. This list includes relevant metadata ontology IDs and labels to tag models with.
- d. The SME adds new terms or removes existing ones and approves the final version of the gross-anatomical terms list. The final authority lies with the SME. If there are multiple SMEs, the SME team is responsible for reaching consensus. The SME then shares the final list with the Medical Illustrator.
- e. The Medical Illustrator evaluates the list against what can be derived from existing data (Visible Human data or other). They also provide a time and cost estimate for model design which is used to help prioritize organ model design.
- f. The SME reviews the edited list and evaluates whether any additional spatial references or landmarks are required in order to be able to register or explore tissue blocks.
- g. The Medical Illustrator communicates what material is needed to produce the first iteration of the model. This entails:
 - i. Clarification of the organ list - i.e. naming conventions, groupings, and if there are many, how they will be designated. The result of this effort will be reflected in the structure list as a complete listing of every object that will be created and how it will be labelled and tagged.
 - ii. Whether existing data can be used as a guide for the modeling process (such as Visible Human data, MRIs, CTs etc).
 - iii. Whether an existing 3D model can be used (e.g., an existing knee model or a model from a different species as for lymph node).
 - iv. Whether multiple versions of the organ are needed (e.g., left vs. right; male vs. female).
 - v. Whether the model is to be adapted from clinical data or should be designed to reflect textbook anatomy.
 - vi. Organs include sub-structures and vasculature as defined by the SME.
 - vii. The Medical Illustrator and the SME decide together what data is to be used.
 - viii. If needed, the PI can specify requirements for the data to be included (e.g., to exploit synergies with other efforts such as the Allen Brain Atlas) or help obtain a dataset that can be used for the modeling process.

Step 4: Reference Object Construction

Once requirements from the PI and SME have been captured, modeling work begins. The Medical Illustrator produces 3D reference objects from Visible Human or other data identified by SMEs or the PI using standard industry tools such as Autodesk Maya, ZBrush, 3DSlicer and Blender.

- The Medical Illustrator builds a first version of the model.
- The Medical Illustrator informs the Senior Research Analyst-Biologist about their progress and any roadblocks encountered, either in their weekly meeting or via email.

- The Senior Research Analyst-Biologist involves the PI to make decisions about content or if the SME is unresponsive.
- The Medical Illustrator shares a draft of the model with the SME, the Senior Research Analyst-Biologist, and the PI as needed. The Senior Research Analyst-Biologist ensures every party has access to the model and tools needed to review the model.
- The Medical Illustrator makes sure the new organ object fits in the overall Human Reference Atlas body and makes the model available via [GitHub](#).

Step 5: SME Review

3D modeling and reviewing is an iterative, complex process that can be computationally expensive. Web-based technologies allow anyone with an internet connection and an updated web browser to load 3D models, inspect them from various angles, read through the hierarchy of substructures with the 3D object, and even adjust the lighting and other scene-related settings to ensure that all potential problems can be identified. Procedures for using these tools in the review process are found below.

- During the review process, meetings should be a last resort in order to use time efficiently. Emails and annotated screenshots are the preferred means of communication.
- The Medical Illustrator uploads a review version of the given model to the [GitHub repository](#) used for staging.
- The SME reviews both the 3D reference object and the anatomical structure nomenclature (shared by the Senior Research Analyst-Biologist) when the model is completed.
- Adjustments are made to both 3D reference model and nomenclature as needed after the SME's review.
- The Medical Illustrator shares a direct link to the 3D model on GitHub with the SME(s).
- The SME downloads the GLB version of the model to their computer.
- The SME uses [Babylon.js Sandbox](#) to view the 3D model in their browser using Firefox or Chrome. A video tutorial on how to download the 3D model and then view it in Babylon can be found [here](#) or written directions [here](#).
- The SME provides feedback on the model to the Medical Illustrator via email. Annotated screenshots work well in communicating suggested changes. These changes can relate to the accurate positioning and shape of structures, the naming, and the relationship between the structures and substructures.
- A final review of both the 3D reference model and nomenclature is organized by the Senior Research Analyst-Biologist to ensure harmonization with the corresponding ASCT+B table.
- If needed, the Senior Research Analyst-Biologist arranges a meeting with the SME(s) to discuss details.
- The Medical Illustrator incorporates changes suggested by the SME(s) and then shares them back to SME(s) for approval.
- Completed organs are shared with SME(s) for their final approval.

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- Next, the System Architect and the PI review the model and share comments with the Medical Illustrator and SME(s).
- Progress and final approvals are tracked by the Senior Research Analyst-Biologist with input from the Medical Illustrator and the PI in a document that is available on request.

Step 6: Publishing

The publishing process is detailed and guided by the [SOP: Using 3D Reference Objects](#) and the SOP: 3D reference organ ontology crosswalk.

Optional: Organs shared by other teams

If an SME wants to share an existing 3D reference object, the object in question should be delivered to the Medical Illustrator in one of the following formats:

- FBX
- STL
- OBJ
- VTK
- NIFTI

References and Definitions

The below references and definitions were used in writing this Standard Operating Procedure. When available, definitions were taken from the [HuBMAP Dictionary](#), and aligned with standard terminologies used in relevant fields.

References

- 3D Model Viewer:
<https://sandbox.babylonjs.com/>
- 3D models are stored on GitHub:
<https://github.com/hubmapconsortium/ccf-3d-reference-object-library>
- Published, DOI'd CCF-Releases are stored on GitHub:
<https://github.com/hubmapconsortium/ccf-releases>
- 3D models are featured on the CCF Portal:
<https://hubmapconsortium.github.io/ccf/pages/ccf-3d-reference-library.html>
- CCF Exploration User Interface (EUI):
<https://hubmapconsortium.github.io/ccf-ui/home>

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Glossary

3D collision The intersection of bounding volumes or polygon meshes detected by an algorithm. Semantic annotation ontology term associated with a 3D object that can be used as an object name and to search for or filter the object.

3D model: A 3D model is a digital object, consisting of vertices and edges, which, when taken together, can form a potentially endless variety of primitive (e.g., cubes, spheres, cones) and complex shapes (such as organs). 3D models come in many formats with various capabilities and limitations (OBJ, FBX, GLB, see below). We use GLB and FBX as output formats.

3D reference object: Polygon mesh of 3D objects (here, anatomical structures), their object node hierarchy, materials and surface colour/texture, all in a spatial context.

Anatomical structures: Parts of the body in defined locations and regions, including the surface, internal organs and tissues. These structures may be described by gross or microscopic morphology and include functional tissue units and highly organized cellular ecosystems (such as alveoli in the lungs).

ASCT+B Tables: see [HuBMAP Glossary](#).

Bimodal network: A network involving two node types and the relationships between them.

Biomarkers: Molecular, histological, morphological, radiological, physiological or anatomical features that help to characterize the biological state of the body. Here we focus on the molecular markers that can be measured to characterize a cell type.

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Cell types: Mammalian cells are biological units with a defined function that typically have a nucleus and cytoplasm surrounded by a membrane. Each cell type may have broad common functions across organs and specialized functions or morphological or molecular features within each organ or region (for example, epithelial cells in the skin, lungs and kidneys may have shared and specialized functions according to tissue localization).

Common Coordinate Framework (CCF): see [HuBMAP Glossary](#).

Crosswalk: An ontological mapping of anatomical structure terms in the 3D reference object files to the anatomical structure terms in the ASCT+B tables.

Exploration User Interface (EUI): see [HuBMAP Glossary](#).

FBX file format: 3D file format specification, see <https://code.blender.org/2013/08/fbx-binary-file-format-specification/>

GitHub: an online service for version control and code-sharing

GLB file format: 3D file format specification, see <https://docs.fileformat.com/3d/glb/>

Healthy tissue: Pathologically unremarkable tissue that can be used to derive the function of healthy cells. What counts as healthy is influenced by normal ageing, underlying comorbidities and medical interventions before tissue donation.

Ontology: A set of subject area concepts (here, anatomical structures, cell types and biomarkers), their properties and the relationships between them. Examples include Uberon, Foundational Model of Anatomy, and Cell Ontology.

OBJ file format: 3D file format specification, see <https://www.cs.cmu.edu/~mbz/personal/graphics/obj.html>

Partonomy: A classification hierarchy that represents part-whole relationships.

Polygon mesh: A polygon mesh is a collection of vertices, edges and faces defining the shape of a polyhedral object (here the 3D reference objects that define anatomical structures).

Registration User Interface (RUI): see [HuBMAP Glossary](#).

Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs): Describe team member responsibilities and outline procedures, which must be followed to support the reproducibility of scientific research.

Typology: A classification that represents general types (here, cell types and biomarker types).

Visible Human (VH): The Visible Human Male and Visible Human datasets are provided by the National Library of Medicine (NLM).